

Resource Scheduling Allocation for Optical and Radio Converged Architecture in 6G networks

Sandra Arnaout, Md Arifur Rahman, Sławomir Hausman, and Piotr Korbel
IS-Wireless, Pulawska Plaza, ul. Pulawska 45b, 05-500 Piaseczno, Poland

Institute of Electronics, Lodz University of Technology, Al. Politechniki 10, Łódź, 93-590, Poland
s.arnaout@is-wireless.com ; a.rahman@is-wireless.com ; slawomir.hausman@p.lodz.pl ; and
piotr.korbel@p.lodz.pl

ABSTRACT

The work reports the resource allocation algorithms for optimum resource allocation over a time and wavelength division multiplexing passive optical network (TWDM-PON) architecture, addressing optical types of system resources, focusing on the optical distribution network. A search algorithm based on Branch and Bound (BB) is adopted to optimize the bandwidth and wavelength allocation to ensure the optimal utilization of resources of the networks. The allocation of the resources is optimized by considering current demands of different services and mapping the services to optical network unit (ONU). In this work, the proposed BB algorithm solves the bandwidth and wavelengths allocation problem to maximize the utilization of the resources.

Keywords: PON, resource scheduling algorithm, optical resource management, bandwidth, and wavelengths.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Next Generation networks (NG networks) are expected to provide the necessary infrastructure and capabilities to enable emerging applications and use cases. In the optical and radio converged network architecture, where the optical and radio communication technologies are integrated, the resources are limited, so it is crucial to utilize the available resources in an efficient way to meet the diverse needs of different demands related to different applications. The resource allocation should be allocated in a dynamic way considering several optimization factors such as the availability of resources in the network, the demands of different applications, services, and scalability. Therefore, in this work, we highlight the importance of allocating resources mechanism by dynamically allocating these resources including bandwidth and wavelengths based on the demands of different types of services, comparing our proposed algorithm with other basic allocation algorithms and analyzing the efficiency of bandwidth utilization while satisfying the demands of the services.

2. PROPOSED RESOURCE SCHEDULING ALGORITHM AND METHODOLOGIES

In this work, we consider the utilization of resources in a dynamic way and three types of services. The services are belonging to enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) with bandwidth requirements [1~10 Gbps], ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) with a few hundred of Mbps requirements, and massive machine-type communications (mMTC) with bandwidth requirements of kbps, respectively. We also consider several ONUs and each ONU is serving specific service demand, and the maximum bandwidth considered here is 40Gbps. Using different types of transmission containers (T-CONTs), we allocate the bandwidth in a more efficient way to the end users and consider we have four wavelengths each with 10Gbps in the considered architecture. Moreover, to allocate the resources efficiently, we formulate an Integer Linear programming (ILP) problem to efficiently select the bandwidths and wavelengths that can satisfy the demands and provide maximum utilization of the resources. Therefore, we propose a branch and bound algorithm that explores the entire search space and finds an optimal solution that satisfies all the considered constraints of the ILP problem. To showcase, the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, we compare the service demands satisfaction and bandwidth utilization performance with two baseline algorithms (i.e., the fix allocation algorithm allocates resources in a deterministic and the random allocation algorithm allocates resources randomly). The simulation results show that our proposed algorithm satisfies the service demands of the mapped combination of the ONUs with T-CONT without exceeding the total available bandwidths of the considered system architecture. Consequently, we illustrate that the proposed algorithm is much more efficient than the other baseline algorithms to satisfy the demands. For our future work, we further enhance the algorithm by considering dynamic topologies and predicting the traffic load of the networks.

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